

ISic1367

I.Sicily inscription 1367

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. □ □ □

1. Ἐνθάδε κίτε

2. Ῥοδίνη· ἔζησεν

3. ἔτη εἰ[κ]οσι πέν(τε)

4. ἔτελεύτησεν

5. δὲ τῆ πρὸ [ι]α εἰ

6. δῶν Νοβεμβρί

7. ων □

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493802

EDCS 39101747

PHI 140872

PHI 175601

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0548 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9484

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